

INTRODUCTION OF A RELIABILITY MEASURE IN MISSING DATA APPROACH FOR ROBUST SPEECH RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the problem of robust speech recognition in noisy conditions in the framework of hidden Markov models (HMMs) and missing feature imputation techniques. It presents a new statistical approach to the detection and estimation of unreliable features based on a probabilistic measure and Gaussian mixture model (GMM) representing clean speech distribution. In the estimation process, the GMM is compensated using parameters of the statistical model of additive background noise. The GMM means are used to estimate the clean speech features. The GMM imputed values and the noisy signal are combined proportionally to a probabilistic reliability measure to estimate the clean speech. The reliability measure allows us to avoid to use a hard decision threshold to decompose the data into reliable and unreliable features and consequently reduces the risk of missclassification. GMM based technique is less complex than the corresponding HMM based estimation and gives similar improvement in the recognition performance. Once unreliable features are replaced by the estimated clean speech features, the entire set of spectral features is transformed to the MFCC (Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficient) feature domain. The MFCCs which are characterized by a higher baseline recognition rate are used for final recognition using continuous density hidden Markov models (CDHMMs) with diagonal covariance matrices.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent works have shown that the application of the missing feature approach in speech and speaker recognition under noisy conditions improves the recognition rates [1–6]. In this approach, the time-frequency representation of the noisy speech signal is partitioned into reliable and unreliable regions according to noise masking criteria.

In the framework of this approach two main techniques have been implemented in the classification process: *marginalisation* - when only reliable data are used, *data imputation* - when unreliable data are estimated.

In this paper, we propose a new method for data imputation based on a probabilistic reliability measure and Gaussian mixture model (GMM). Noisy signal data and model based imputed data are combined proportionally to the reliability measure to obtain an estimate of clean speech signal data. This method offers the advantage of a smooth transition between reliable and unreliable data in the estimation process, reducing the effect of missclassification errors.

Once the unreliable data are replaced by the estimated clean speech data, the entire data is transformed to the cepstral domain for final recognition with the second set of models (hidden Markov models (HMMs)) trained on clean speech.

The method proposed in this paper, based on two sets of statistical models (GMMs and HMMs), is applied to continuous-density hidden Markov model based speech recognizers and evaluated on the TIDIGIT database for several noisy conditions.

2 RELIABILITY MEASURE

In the missing feature theory, the data are divided into *reliable* and *unreliable* segments. Normally, the segmentation is obtained using a threshold calculated from the estimated noise features [4, 6]. In this paper, the two-state segmentation with hard decision threshold is replaced by a smooth segmentation using a probabilistic reliability measure. This measure can vary between zero (totally unreliable) and one (totally reliable). The SNR measure gives an information on the relative importance of both noise and signal and is well suited to detect reliable and unreliable regions.

The prior SNR is defined as

$$SNR_{prior}(\omega) = \frac{|x(\omega)|^2}{|n(\omega)|^2} \quad (1)$$

where $|x(\omega)|$ and $|n(\omega)|$ are the clean speech and noise signal magnitudes for frequency ω of the spectro-temporal representation of the signals. Under the hypothesis that speech and noise are additive, the clean speech signal can be estimated as $|\hat{x}(\omega)| = |y(\omega)| - |\hat{n}(\omega)|$.

In previous approaches [3–6], features are declared reliable if the prior SNR exceeds a fixed threshold value τ . Substituting the clean speech magnitude by its estimate in Eq. 1, we obtain the SNR detection criterion for reliable data:

$$\frac{(|y(\omega)| - |\hat{n}(\omega)|)^2}{|\hat{n}(\omega)|^2} > \tau \quad (2)$$

which can also be expressed as

$$|y(\omega)| > (\sqrt{\tau} + 1) \cdot |\hat{n}(\omega)|. \quad (3)$$

The reliability measure Ψ is defined as the probability for the SNR to be greater than τ . If the noise is normally distributed in the spectral domain, the function Ψ is

$$\Psi(y(\omega)|\hat{\mu}_n(\omega), \hat{\sigma}_n^2(\omega)) = \int_{-\infty}^{\frac{y(\omega)}{\sqrt{\tau+1}}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}|\hat{\sigma}_n(\omega)|} e^{-\left(\frac{x - \hat{\mu}_n(\omega)}{2\hat{\sigma}_n^2(\omega)}\right)^2} dx. \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mu}_n(\omega)$ and $\hat{\sigma}_n(\omega)^2$ are, respectively, the estimated mean and variance of the noise and $y(\omega)$ is the noisy speech signal.

3 ESTIMATION OF CLEAN DATA

To cope with unreliable data in speech recognition, three approaches have been proposed:

- In the first approach only the reliable data is used during recognition process. In this case, the data are divided into reliable and unreliable sets, and the marginal densities, representing the reliable data are used to calculate the emission probability in the HMMs.
- In the second approach the probability density functions associated with the missing data are integrated over a certain interval to obtain the emission probability for each state of the HMMs. Several methods have been proposed [7–10].
- In the third approach the unreliable data are estimated. This approach offers the advantage that other than filter bank features can be used, *e.g.* Mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) which generally give better baseline recognition results.

A HMMs based data imputation method has been proposed in [7, 8]. The recognized state sequence obtained using only the reliable data is used to impute the unreliable data. The unreliable data are replaced by a weighted sum of the means of the distributions of the recognized state sequence.

When using time-dependent statistical models such as HMMs, the state sequence needed for the estimation of the unreliable data is hidden. If an error in the decoded sequence occurs, it can influence the recognition in the

second feature domain. Therefore the method for the estimation of the unreliable data proposed in this paper, is based on time-independent Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) instead of HMMs. It models roughly the distribution of the speech data. This is clearly a suboptimal model, but sufficient and computationally efficient for data imputation. The GMM likelihood for a vector of parameters $X = [x(1), \dots, x(\omega), \dots, x(\Omega)]^T$ is defined as:

$$p(X|\lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^M P(i) \cdot \prod_{\omega=1}^{\Omega} \Phi(x(\omega), \mu(\omega, i), \sigma^2(\omega, i)) \quad (5)$$

where M represents the number of Gaussian distributions, $P(i)$, $\mu(\omega, i)$ and $\sigma^2(\omega, i)$ are, respectively, the weighting factor, mean and variance for Gaussian i .

The means and variances of the GMM are compensated to cope with the additive noise, similarly to parallel model combination (PMC) [11].

The means and the variances of each Gaussian distribution are transformed into the magnitude spectral domain using an inverse log-normal approximation:

$$\mu_{in}(\omega, i) = \exp\left(\mu(\omega, i) + \frac{\sigma^2(\omega, i)}{2}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{in}^2(\omega, i) = \mu_{in}^2(\omega, i) \cdot (\exp(\sigma^2(\omega, i)) - 1) \quad (7)$$

These means and variances are modified to include the distortion introduced by the additive noise. Means and variances of the noise are estimated during speech pauses.

$$\tilde{\mu}_{in}(\omega, i) = \mu_{in}(\omega, i) + \mu_n(\omega) \quad (8)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{in}^2(\omega, i) = \sigma_{in}^2(\omega, i) + \sigma_n^2(\omega) \quad (9)$$

The means and variances of the GMM are transformed back into the log-spectral domain.

$$\tilde{\mu}(\omega, i) = \log\left(\frac{\tilde{\mu}_{in}^2(\omega, i)}{\sqrt{\tilde{\mu}_{in}^2(\omega, i) + \tilde{\sigma}_{in}^2(\omega, i)}}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2(\omega, i) = \log\left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{in}^2(\omega, i)}{\tilde{\mu}_{in}^2(\omega, i)} + 1\right) \quad (11)$$

Using this noisy GMM, the weighting factor associated with each distribution is computed as follows:

$$\gamma(i|Y, \tilde{\lambda}) = \frac{P(i) \prod_{\omega=1}^{\Omega} \Phi(y(\omega), \tilde{\mu}(\omega, i), \tilde{\sigma}^2(\omega, i))}{p(Y|\tilde{\lambda})} \quad (12)$$

The estimated clean signal $\hat{x}(\omega)$ is the combination of the noisy signal $y(\omega)$ and a weighted sum of the clean GMM means:

$$\hat{x}(\omega) = (1 - \Psi(y(\omega))) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^M \gamma(i|Y, \tilde{\lambda}) \cdot \mu(\omega, i) + \Psi(y(\omega)) \cdot y(\omega) \quad (13)$$

When the reliability is high ($\Psi(y(\omega)) \sim 1$) the influence of the noisy speech signal is dominant. On the other hand, in low reliability regions, the estimated value is dominant.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The recognition system proposed in this paper was developed using Hidden Markov Toolkit (HTK). The time-frequency representation of the signal is provided by a 17 bands Bark filter bank. Digits models were trained on TIDIGIT database down-sampled to a frequency of 8kHz using word models with eight emitting states and three Gaussians per state. TIDIGIT database was used for the digits recognition experiments using 100 utterances from 65 speakers extracted randomly from the database. Noises from the NOISEX database were added to obtain test utterances.

Recognition experiments have been performed using the Bark filter bank features and Mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) with energy and first and second derivatives. The MFCCs are calculated from the filter bank features and the first 12 cepstral coefficients are used.

The GMMs representing the clean speech distribution have been trained on the complete TIDIGIT database for 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, and 256 Gaussians.

All the recognition results express the digit recognition accuracy as a function of the SNR of the noisy signal. The accuracy is defined as the percentage of correctly recognized digits minus the percentage of inserted digits.

Figure 1: Influence of the value of τ on the recognition performances for Lynx helicopter noise in filter bank and MFCC domains

4.1 Influence of τ

The first experiment compares the results for different values of τ for the soft decision threshold in order to

find the value which gives the best results. Values from -2dB to 10 dB have been tested for several noisy conditions. We found that threshold values of $\tau = 2$ dB and $\tau = 6$ dB give the best recognition performances in filter-bank and mel-cepstral domains respectively. Results are presented in Fig.1 for Lynx helicopter noise. Similar results have been obtained with white Gaussian noise and babble noise. The GMM with 64 Gaussians was used to model the clean speech distribution.

4.2 Influence of the number of Gaussian distributions in the GMM

The second experiment investigates the influence of the number of Gaussian distributions in the GMM model. We found that a number of 64 Gaussian distributions offers a good compromise between the performance and the computation complexity. Fig. 2 presents the recognition performances for different numbers of Gaussians in the GMM model for Lynx helicopter noise. It can be observed that passing from 64 to 128 or 256 Gaussians does not improve significantly the recognition performance. Similar results were obtained with white Gaussian and babble noises.

Figure 2: Influence of the number of Gaussian distributions in the GMM on the recognition performances for Lynx helicopter noise in filter bank and MFCC domains

4.3 Comparison of several methods

The last experiment compares the proposed method with other reference methods. These methods are:

- *Baseline*: The HMM recognition is performed on the noisy data.
- *General Spectral Subtraction*: The parameters are enhanced using a general spectral subtraction with $\alpha = 1.5$ and $\beta = 0.002$ [12, 13].

- *Marginal densities:* Reliable features are extracted using missing feature detector proposed in [6] and marginal densities are calculated in the recognition phase.
- *Two-state statistical estimation:* Reliable parameters are extracted using missing feature detector proposed in [14] and the data are enhanced as in Eq. 13 with only two values of Ψ : $\Psi(y(\omega)) = 1$ for reliable data and $\Psi(y(\omega)) = 0$ for unreliable data.
- *Smooth statistical estimation:* The data are enhanced using Eq.13.

Figure 3: Recognition accuracy for Lynx helicopter noise.

Fig. 3 shows the accuracy of digits recognition as a function of SNR for five investigated methods using filter bank features and MFCCs. The method proposed in this paper outperforms other methods in the whole range of SNRs in the MFCC domain, especially from -5 to 10 dB. The results presented are obtained for Lynx helicopter noise, but similar enhancement was obtained for other types of noise such as babble noise, white Gaussian noise and factory noise.

5 Conclusion

This paper has demonstrated that the introduction of a measure of reliability and a soft decision threshold for data imputation technique leads to improvement in the recognition results. The estimated clean spectral features can be transformed to the MFCC domain, and derivatives can also be used. Using a GMM for clean speech estimation reduces the computational complexity of the processing when compared with HMMs methods.

6 References

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